

USE OF INTERNET DATA IN PRIMARY CLASS READING LESSONS

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Abstract: This article discusses the use of Internet information in elementary reading classes. The importance of information and communication technologies in education is also described.

Key words: technology, perception, communication, internet, visual and audio, educational system.

The first stage of the human sense of knowledge is live observation, that is, perception of things and events around. The principle of instructiveness makes it easier to understand and connects theoretical knowledge with life and practice. This principle increases interest in the studied phenomena, helps to acquire knowledge more thoroughly. According to Ibn Sina, at the beginning of his studies, a person studies the external properties of a thing, he can create direct knowledge on his own by seeing its original and image. The definition of any thing is known as a means of proving its existence, that is, things and events consist of properties determined by some science. This contentment illuminates only one aspect of the instructional principle in teaching. By perceiving existing things or their images, a person has an idea about objective reality, and in this way, an opportunity to describe them correctly arises.

From the teachings of the scientist, human things and events, their characteristics are seeing (visual), hearing (audial), tasting, smelling. it is known to receive by feeling (tactile), the main part of them, i.e. more than ninety percent, is absorbed by sight and hearing. Perception of things and events is carried out through the external sense organs, and it also happens by grasping and seeing. Touching allows us to know the heat, coldness, wetness, dryness, hardness, softness, heaviness, lightness, shape, etc. of the perceived object. And the skin and muscles are sensory instruments. Nerves transmit this sensation to the muscles and skin. Based on this, it can be said that educational materials learned through the Internet are also learned through sight and hearing. It turns out that Internet materials are relatively easy to digest.

In primary classes, it is appropriate to show the objects themselves or to get acquainted with them directly in nature, and to use handouts consisting of the objects themselves in the lessons. Guides with picture instructions: although the effect of landscape images, slides and slides is less effective, it is possible to form

a holistic idea of one or another thing through them. A set of mixed instructional tools is also an important element of educational equipment. They help to create, quickly change and combine different instructional situations during the lesson. For this, drawing materials are used or pictures and drawings are drawn on the board with chalk and various notes are made.

These tools include magnetic boards and flanges. Their didactic capabilities are the same. They are of incomparable value in teaching elementary school students, but audio-visual guides and sometimes other instructional tools are also necessary in the educational process. It has the following different options:

1. Show an educational film in the introductory lesson on the topic of processing objects in the program and use film clips, film fragments, slides, slide films and charts in subsequent lessons.
2. Development of special issues of the topic using slides, slides, tables, demonstrated experiments, film fragments and film clips. Show educational films in the generalization lesson on this topic.
3. Presentation of slide films, slides, film clips and an educational film at the end of the lesson together with the teacher's explanation.
4. To expand the imagination of students, to ensure the completeness of the content of the concepts formed in them, the development of educational material using one series of screen guides and the use of another set of them to strengthen knowledge.

Given the various didactic tasks and possibilities of instructional tools, it is required to use them in a complex manner. Only in this case, solving the cognitive task of the lesson can rise to the highest level. At the same time, the use of different instructional weapons is justified only when it is necessary to cover various aspects of the studied phenomenon. Because each of these aspects can be covered convincingly and clearly with the help of a certain type of demonstrability. When choosing instructional tools, it is necessary to compare their capabilities with the characteristics of each educational subject and the content of each lesson. Instructional manuals are provided to students using different types of instructional materials:

1. Natural instruction - requires students to be introduced to existing objects, plants, animals, minerals, etc. Natural Instructability can be demonstrated both in the classroom and during field trips.
2. Volumetric indicativeness is a reflection of the volume of the existing world. It will consist of photographs, drawings, film and slides.

3. Sound instruction - use of sound tools to express sound images, listening to gramophone records and tape recorders, watching sound movies.

4. Symbolic and graphic instruction - maps, plans, schemes, drawings and diagrams. They develop thinking due to the fact that they reflect the existing reality in a conditional generalized symbolic form.

All these types of instruction are used in the school from the first grade to the tenth grade, but, naturally, taking into account the age of the students in the elementary grades, entrusting them with direct observations, thinking and acting on this basis, in the upper grades, the independent students and according to the development of logical thinking, it will be appropriate to use more symbolic and graphic observations. Prescriptiveness is essential when students do not have a specific idea of what is to be learned. But it should also be remembered that not preparing for the presentation of instruction manuals or choosing them incorrectly will only cause harm. Today, even in the national education system, the Internet is becoming a part of the teacher's life and work. Because it has become the most convenient and familiar source of new information.

In addition to these, they also use it to organize online classes in their activities:

- organize students' study in the classroom and outside the classroom;
- help students to use the Internet correctly;
- organize their students to work as a team;
- increase students' access to information.

All this allows the professional activity of the teacher to be carried out qualitatively. For this purpose, teachers should do the following:

- ❖ determining the amount of tasks assigned to students;
- ❖ using modern internet materials along with their traditional teaching methods;
- ❖ observing colleagues' lessons via the Internet, using their experience in their practice if necessary

In addition, not only teachers, but also students can find the necessary educational materials in the classroom or library via the Internet, share the found materials with their friends, and submit their knowledge and homework to their teacher via the Internet. The constant communication of the teacher and students through the Internet ensures the effectiveness of this activity.

The Internet search engine provides readers with a choice of multimedia information in a variety of areas. Students will also have access to a variety of reference books, encyclopedias, and educational materials to keep up with the

latest news. The possibilities of the Internet are so great today that it makes it possible to find a solution to any problem at home or at school, without moving from your seat. The data warehouse is accessed through: libraries, sound libraries, film libraries. Working with search servers of this form is convenient and easy when you know exactly what to search for.

There are various multimedia materials on the Internet. Students find it difficult to choose what is important and necessary among the available materials. Therefore, it is considered appropriate to turn to search servers. In them, such servers, which refer to various topics, begin to search for the necessary resource according to the requirements of users.

The use of Internet technologies by teachers in their classes is causing both classes and academic subjects to go beyond the established time standards. The reason is that the student's interest in acquiring knowledge does not stop at the end of the lesson. If the child is interested, he will be sought.

Schools around the world are moving to a new stage of Internet technologies, that is, to the use of alternative educational elements in the curriculum. They want to solve some educational problems with this. It is intended to provide an opportunity not only for teachers, but also for students to realize their educational goals, expand their worldview, gain knowledge, and form their personality correctly. Students can learn from various sites at their convenience. The main responsibility for helping children and guiding them is given to parents.

In addition to educating and raising children, Internet technologies also cause the problem of children's saturation with information. In addition, students are getting false information from some incompetent sites. Readers should access the Internet stream of information and receive ready-made information, as well as have their own point of view on the topic at hand. The reader cannot solve this problem independently. This means that the reader cannot be left alone in the flow of information. In short, a national school cannot be imagined without modern information technologies. Teaching using computer technologies is becoming a normal educational process for teachers and students of elementary grades. But in order to use the Internet wisely, it is first necessary to work at the level of children, to form their spirituality in a healthy way, and to purify their psyche.

Today, the Internet covers the entire social life. The number of Internet users and informative pages is increasing day by day. The Internet is primarily a data network. The sheer volume of data is turning the Internet into an unparalleled

network and resource for information retrieval. Not only teachers, students also use this network and get the information they need. Today's students look for knowledge and information easily from the Internet, sitting at home, not from books. Today, students also feel the need to effectively use Internet resources. Both parents and schools should focus on their students' effective use of web resources, e.g. It is desirable for them to participate in online conferences, monitor their use in the creation of their sites, and direct them to useful work. In conclusion, the use of modern information communication technologies in primary classes helps students to think independently, expand their creative research and logical thinking, connect what they learned in lessons with life, and increase their interest in the lesson. Teachers effectively use the conditions created based on such modern requirements and organize lessons based on advanced pedagogical and information communication technologies, which guarantees the quality of the educational process.

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